

Legal corpora: A trial lesson with translators and lawyers

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Legal translators are often confronted with the peculiarities of legal writing, especially if they have undergone little training in legal matters (Bhatia, 1997; Tiersma, 1999; Williams, 2011). At the same time, both novice and experienced lawyers may find it difficult to understand legal texts in a second language due to linguistic shortcomings. This paper aims at exploring if second language professionals, scholars and students can learn the genre of the law through the medium of online specialized corpora. A trial lesson was given to 8 participants (4 translators, 1 academic student, and 3 lawyers) who attended a 3-hour workshop and were introduced to online legal corpora. This paper shows that the Internet is a rich source of free legal corpora which can be used for linguistic and translation purposes. It is concluded that professionals, scholars, and students can be trained to acquire the technological skills which will help them overcome the linguistic intricacies of the language of law.

Keywords: Legal Corpora; Legal English; Legal Translations; Online Corpora; Specialized Translations

1. Introduction

The research topic of this paper focuses on the use of corpora for legal translation training and practice (See also Biel, 2010; Biel, Engberg, Ruano, & Sosoni, 2019). In particular, the research question focuses on whether online corpora can help deliver accurate legal translations and expedite the translation process (Monzó-Nebot, 2008), provided that users are trained in information retrieval and are acquainted with corpus search syntax (Raído, 2014; Zanettin, Bernardini, & Stewart, 2014). The aim of this paper is, hence, to explore whether professional legal translators (with more than 10 years of experience), junior legal translators (with 1-5 years of experience), bachelor academic students, novice lawyers (with 4 years of experience) and experienced lawyers (with more than 10 years of experience) can be trained

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in online specialized corpora to tackle English legal texts and legal translations. To this aim, a trial lesson was carried out, and a 3-hour workshop was organized, in order to equip them with *ad hoc* technological tools. This was in line with the EMT model, which recommends specific technological skills (Toudic & Krause, 2017).

This trial lesson partly parallels the research carried out by O'Neil (1998), who examined whether a medical professional or a medical translator is better at translating medical texts. With legal discourse the *dilemma* is the same: a non-lawyer linguist may overlook important legal details or concepts whereas a lawyer may have problems with the linguistic aspects of the text. For this reason, it was considered sensible to organize a workshop with both translators (either experienced or not) and lawyers. This approach has also been followed by Orlando (2017).

The first part of this paper will focus on the multifaceted features of legal language which make it peculiar and, sometimes, intricate. Therefore, the hallmarks of legal writing and the skills required for legal translations will be brought to the fore. Then, specialized corpora will be tackled, as they are tools which can help meet the linguistic challenges of technical texts. Thirdly, a trial lesson will be outlined. The trial lesson was carried out with the aim of introducing online legal corpora to both novice and experienced translators and lawyers, with the view to training them and helping them address the linguistic intricacies of the language of law. The workshop outcomes will be qualitatively analyzed in the last part of this paper, together with the participants' perspectives on legal language tools and their newly acquired skills.

2. Background

Legal language is claimed to be particularly pedantic and archaic (Bhatia, 1997; Tiersma, 1999; Williams, 2011), mostly because of its reliance on complex sentence structures and syntax, which are far from everyday language. Some scholars have, in fact, defined it as “wordy, unclear, pompous and dull” (Mellinkoff, 1963, p. 24) whereas others claim that legal writing is “the largest body of poorly written literature ever created” (Lindsey, 1990, p. 2, as cited in Coulthard & Johnson, 2010). Furthermore, legal language differs not only on the basis of different legal systems, but also within countries which share the same legal traditions (Yankova, 2017). Therefore, the legal jargon is challenging, especially if one has to translate it (Chromá, 2011; Prieto Ramos, 2011). For this reason, several skills are required for legal translations.

It is generally assumed that in order to translate a legal text, translators need not only linguistic, but also legal expertise (Giampieri, 2016; Northcott &

Brown, 2006) and, ideally, they should be acquainted with comparative law (De Groot & Van Laer, 2008). It is in fact claimed that “(k)nowledge of the language pairs and the two legal systems involved plus awareness of the translation context . . . are all required” in legal translations (Orozco-Jutorán & Sánchez-Gijón, 2011, p. 25). This paves the way for the general assumption that the best legal translators are “those trained in both translation and law” (Prieto Ramos, 2011, p. 13). Unfortunately, this is not always the case—See also the parallel argumentation developed by O' Neill (1998) as far as medical translation is concerned. Scholars and lecturers, in fact, often lament that translation students lack legal training (Vigier Moreno, 2016) whereas lawyers are increasingly confronted with linguistic issues in legal writing (Ewald, 2008). In addition, translation students lack proper technical and technological competence, which would help them overcome the linguistic intricacies of legal texts. According to the literature, in fact, translating specialized texts (as the legal ones are) has become more a question of using the right tools, than a matter of knowing the right words (Martin, 2011, as cited in Vigier Moreno, 2016). The tight deadlines translators must often abide by, for example, make it impossible to undertake thorough comparative law analysis (Biel, 2008). Hence, it is claimed that technology can help compensate for the lack of legal knowledge, without affecting the quality of legal translations (Monzó-Nebot, 2008).

3. Method

3.1. Corpora

A corpus is a collection of texts in electronic form which are gathered for linguistic analysis (Sinclair, 1991). The software, or interface which analyzes corpora, generates concordance lines (also referred to as 'concordances', Zanettin, 2012, p. 143; Gatto, 2014, p. 23). Concordance lines are strings of text reporting the searched word, also called 'node word' (Zanettin, 2012; Gatto, 2014), and dispose it at the center of the text, in a way which is suitable for the reader (Gatto, 2014).

Corpora can also show collocations. Collocations are patterns of language usage (Sinclair, 1991; Gatto, 2014) and concern the frequent co-occurrence of lexical items or words (Clear, 1993; Lehecka, 2015). The examples (1) 'butter goes rancid', while (2) 'bread goes stale' when they (3) 'go bad' (Palmer, 1981; Baker, 2011) are generally referred to in order to explain collocations. Corpora can also show the 'key words in context' (KWIC), where the node word is shown at the center of the screen and is surrounded by other words (Zanettin, 2012). These are marked in different colors, depending on their distance from the node word. Another useful term to be acquainted with, is 'lemma'. A lemma is a headword which includes its inflected forms (Anderson

& Corbett, 2017). For example, 'have' is the lemma of the word forms 'has', 'had', and 'having'. A corpus which considers words as lemmas can obviously retrieve more information. Another useful feature that a corpus can be equipped with, is 'part of speech' (POS) tagging. POS tagging (or annotation) labels each word according to its class (e.g., a noun, an adjective, etc.) (Gatto, 2014; Anderson & Corbett, 2017). It goes without saying that such a function is particularly useful for linguistic purposes and research. Corpora are generally consulted because they help users deal with examples of authentic texts. The importance of authenticity in language teaching and learning has been highlighted by the literature, also in the legal field (see Townley & Riazi, 2014).

The *Bononia Legal Corpus* (henceforth the *BoLC*) (Rossini Favretti, Tamburini, & Martelli, 2007), together with the *British Law Report Corpus* (*BLaRC*) and the *Law section of the British National Corpus* (the *BNC-Law*) of The Compleat Lexical Tutor (*Lextutor*) (Cobb, 2004), are online legal corpora which can be used in order to dispel linguistic doubts and check word frequencies. They generate concordance lines and help find collocates in legal texts. For example, the *BoLC* is very useful thanks to its completeness. The *BoLC* is, in fact, composed of a British-English subsection counting over 74 million tokens and an Italian subsection, with almost 65 million tokens. The *BoLC* subsections can be defined as online comparable legal corpora.

The other corpora which will be addressed in this paper, are the *BLaRC* and an extract of the *BNC-Law*, which can be queried on the *Lextutor* online interface (Cobb, 2004). The *BLaRC* is composed of British Law Reports compiled from 2008 to 2010 and it contains 8.8 million words. The *BNC-Law* is composed of 2.2 million words. As can be seen, they tend to be smaller than the *BoLC*. This, however, does not impinge on the quality of the research results. The literature, in fact, claims that legal corpora can be rather small without affecting their quality and representativeness (Bhatia, Langton, & Lung, 2004; Biel, 2010). This is mainly because legal language is very conservative and formulaic *per se* (Bhatia et al., 2004). It goes without saying that legal translation is domain-specific and can be found in a number of different environments. The resources being cited in this paper tend to focus on institutional or supranational translations, yet they do not necessarily account for other types of legal translation which can occur.

3.2. The trial lesson

As outlined above, this paper aims at exploring whether corpus consultation can help deliver fine-grained legal translations and compensate for legal translators' and lawyers' linguistic shortcomings. To this end, a trial lesson was carried out to coach translators and lawyers on how to address the

technicalities of legal texts by means of online *ad hoc* corpora. In order to do so, a 3-hour workshop on online corpora for legal translation was organized. The workshop title was “Legal English, the web and corpora” and was held in the office of a certified training agency. The pedagogic unit which the corpus was based on revolved around ICT skills for technical (legal) translations. In particular, the workshop was organized in two units or modules: (a) foundations of corpus linguistics, and (b) consultation of online legal corpora (i.e., how to generate concordances and search for collocations). As prerequisites, the participants only needed have a good knowledge of English and, possibly, an interest in legal translations or the language of law. The attendants were asked to bring their own computers to the classroom. The learning experience was very practical and it took only 3 hours because it aimed at laying the foundations of corpus consultation for legal translations without committing the participants to a more engaging or demanding learning experience.

Potential attendees were contacted via email, either directly (their email addresses had been sourced from online translators' forums, law firm websites, or from past workshop mailing lists) or indirectly (a workshop brochure had been sent to them by the admission office of Schools for Interpreters and Translators). 8 participants enrolled voluntarily (no compensation was foreseen). In particular, the attendants were 4 translators (2 with 1-5 years of experience and 2 with more than 10); 3 lawyers (1 with 4 years of experience and 2 with more than 10) and 1 student in translation (with no working experience). The professional translators had at least a bachelor's degree in translation studies, and their language pairs were mainly English/Italian; also a Polish/Italian translator enrolled. Their areas of specialization were various (marketing, tourism, business, etc.). Only one experienced translator was used to dealing with legal translations. The student was enrolled in a bachelor's course in translation studies where she practiced technical translation techniques. The lawyers' first language was Italian, and their second language English. They worked in international law firms and dealt with international clients using English as a *lingua franca*. They mainly participated to improve their translation skills, being sometimes confronted with legal texts which they had to translate into English. All the lawyers who participated in this project were self-taught legal translators. The face-to-face workshop was conducted by the first author of this paper: an Italian-English court interpreter and translator with experience in legal translations, a master's degree in economics and law, and one in applied linguistics.

In order to better grasp concepts and perform tasks smoothly, participants were firstly introduced to the linguistics terminology revolving around 'corpus', 'collocation', 'lemma', and KWIC. The corpora dealt with were the

BLaRC, the *BNC-Law* (as part of the Lextutor online interface) and the *BoLC*. These were explained thoroughly: from the search for single words or lemmas in Lextutor, to the complex query syntax and search for collocates in the *BoLC*.

At the end of the workshop, participants filled out a self-administered qualitative questionnaire with factual, behavioral and attitudinal questions (a la Sanjun, 2016). In particular, the questionnaire aimed at understanding the attendants' experience in legal translations; their previous knowledge of corpora; their interest in the workshop and intention to use them in the near future. The questionnaire was composed of 12 questions, either open or closed. The questionnaire results are reported in Appendix 1. The following sections will highlight some tasks which reveal how the participants acquired technical (and technological) knowledge, improved their skills, and applied critical thinking.

3. Results

The paragraphs which follow focus on some tasks which the participants undertook. In particular, the tasks provide instances of how the participants increased their comprehension of and competences in corpus consultation. The terms analyzed were selected on the basis of the lecturer's experience with some challenging legal terms (see Giampieri, 2018b). The results are based on field notes taken by the lecturer during the workshop.

As claimed by the literature, legal language is rich in near-synonyms (Phillips, 2003; Chromà, 2011). For example, if one looks up in a dictionary for the translation of the Italian word '*affitto*', both 'rent' and 'hire' may be proposed as translation equivalents (Collins Online Dictionary). In order to better grasp their differences, if any, the participants were asked, as their first task, to search for collocates of 'rent' and 'hire' in the *BoLC*. In order to do so, they wrote "rent" firstly, then "hire" (both in double inverted commas) in the search field, care being taken to select the 'Get Collocates?' button. The search results proved to be very satisfactory. As a matter of fact, they noticed that 'rent' collocates, amongst others, with 'arrear', 'tenancy', 'payment', 'annual', and 'landlord'; whereas 'hire' with 'vehicle', 'agreement', 'car', 'credit', 'company', and 'hackney'. All of the participants rightly inferred that 'rent' applies to houses and apartments, hence immovable goods; however, 'hire' refers to movable goods, such as cars and hackneys.

As outlined above, translators and lawyers are often confronted with formulaic expressions (Bhatia et al., 2004; Williams, 2013), which follow "a very rigid structure" (Tiersma & Solan, 2012). Hence, they may find it difficult to tackle formulaic patterns in a second language. The second task—called '*costituersi parte civile*'—aimed at teaching how to consult corpora in order to

find translation equivalents, using critical thinking and supplementing corpus consultation with other resources. For this purpose, the participants were prompted to find an equivalent of '*costituirsì parte civile*', which is an Italian phrase used when a party asks for damages in a criminal proceedings. In this case, online dictionaries failed to provide a satisfactory answer, which is what the literature often claims (Andrades Moreno, 2013; Teubert, 2002). For instance, The Collins Online Dictionary proposes 'to associate in an action with the public prosecutor for damages', which finds 0 matches in the *BoLC*. To search for useful results in the *BoLC*, the participants were taught to write every word in inverted commas, then to use squared and round brackets between node words in order to retrieve all occurrences between them. The round brackets should report the word span. For example, the search string "*public*" "*prosecutor*" $[[\{0,7\}$ "*damages*" led to no results (the ' $[[\{0,7\}$ ' command instructs the system to include from 0 to 7 words, or characters, before 'damages'). In light of the lack of results, the participants were prompted to explore other ways in order to translate '*costituirsì parte civile*'. For example, the experienced lawyers proposed to resort to the Italian subsection of the *BoLC*, and search for the collocations and words in context of '*costituirsì parte civile*'. Then, with the help of the translators and of online dictionaries, they back-translated the collocations and searched for the back-translations in the English subsection. In order to make the search as wide as possible, the lecturer suggested considering '*costituirsì*' (infinitive) as a lemma. Although it was stated above that the *BoLC* does not include a search syntax for lemmas, this shortcoming could be compensated for by using the OR operator '|', and brackets. In this way, '*costituirsì*' (past participle) and '*costituì*' (simple past) could also be written in the search string. Therefore, the lecturer suggested the query ("*costituirsì*" | "*costituirsì*" | "*costituì*") "*parte civile*", which instructed the system to search for any of the words in brackets, together with '*parte civile*'. By analyzing the collocates and words in context of the results, the participants (especially lawyers) noticed, amongst others, the following recurrent words and expressions: '*risarcimento del danno*', '*procedimento penale*', and '*penale*'. The participants were then prompted to translate these key words by using online bilingual dictionaries. Therefore, they found the translation of '*risarcimento del danno*' ('damages'); '*procedimento penale*' ('criminal prosecution'), and '*penale*' ('criminal'). Then, they searched these back-translations in the English section of the *BoLC*, in order to see if they could find any interesting results and phrases. An example of a search string they wrote is the following: "*damages*" $[[\{0,6\}$ "*criminal*" $[[\{0,6\}$ "*prosecution*". A few concordance lines were retrieved and the following sentence noticed: 'claim for damages as a result of a criminal prosecution', which the most experienced lawyers agreed on considering an acceptable equivalent. This translation candidate is suggested by the literature (Hebly, Van Dongen, & Lindenbergh, 2014) and by the European

Judicial Network in Civil and Commercial Matter database.¹ Therefore, the participants succeeded in finding a translation of the formulaic expression 'costituersi parte civile'.

The third task, called '*All'epoca dei fatti*', is another formulaic expression often used by lawyers in civil case deeds or documents. It means 'at the time when the litigation arose'. The participants were asked to find a translation in English by resorting to any possible online resources. At the same time, however, they had to corroborate the equivalent candidates in the *BoLC* and verify the number of occurrences. In this way, the participants could both increase their corpus analysis skills and develop critical thinking by consulting other language resources. The *raison d'être* of this search strategy is highlighted by Raido (2014) and Giampieri (2018a; 2018b; 2019). In their case studies, they prove that Web search can lead to translation problem solving. This applies to the challenges of legal translations (Giampieri, 2018a; 2018b; 2019), which are also due to complexities resulting from different legal systems.

The importance of strategic Web search is corroborated by Gallego-Hernández (2015), who reported that experienced translators tend to spend more time acquiring knowledge from the Web, than relying purely on dictionaries. As a matter of fact, all of the participants found an equivalent of '*all'epoca dei fatti*' in 'at the material time', which they sourced freely from the Web (in particular from multilingual databases). Such formulaic expression shows 265 concordance lines in the *BoLC*, which was considered acceptable. The translator with experience in legal translations also searched for "*material*" ("*times*"/"*time*") and surprisingly found 683 concordance lines with 'at the/any material time' and 'at all material times'. In this way, she found another suitable translation candidate (i.e., 'at all material times'), which was later searched for by the lecturer and found in authoritative websites (see Decisions and Orders of the National Labor Relation Board, 2010, p. 207).²

The fourth task focused on the distinction between 'termination' and 'cancellation'. The literature reports that in contract law, 'termination' is often misused and mistaken for 'cancellation' (Giampieri, 2016). In particular, 'cancellation' should be the term to use when a contract is ended because of the non-performance (or default/breach of contract) by a party (UCC, 1972). Nonetheless, 'termination' and/or 'termination for breach' often replaces 'cancellation'; in particular, this occurs in UK legal language. Therefore, the participants were prompted to verify this in the *BLaRC* and were asked to explore whether the lemma 'terminate' collocates with 'breach' or 'default'. In doing so, they were trained how to search for lemmas on the Lextutor interface (i.e., by choosing 'family' in the drop-down menu of the keyword search). They also learned how to find whether a word collocates with

another one (i.e., by writing the two terms, 'breach' and 'default', with no comma, in the field 'with associated words') (see Figure 1).

The screenshot shows the 'Web Concordance - English V.8' interface. At the top, it says 'NEW 14 JAN 2020- SHAKESPE'. Below that, there are navigation links for 'French German Spanish English'. A status bar indicates 'Base Speed = 1 second per million words of corpus' and 'Add more for extras (associated words, family search, sub-corpus)'. The main search area has a 'Keyword(s):' field with 'family' and 'terminate' entered. To the right, it says '(Max chars. 21)' and 'In corpus: BLaRC Law Reports (8.8m)'. Below this, there is an 'OPTION : With associated word(s)' field containing 'breach default' and a 'within 4 words' dropdown menu.

Figure 1. Searching for 'terminate' as a lemma together with the words 'breach' and 'default'.

In this way, the participants retrieved 19 concordance lines, showing phrases such as 'termination for breach', 'termination for fundamental breach', 'terminated without any default', 'terminates without breach'. Therefore, this underpins that in British English, 'termination', and in particular 'termination for breach', are used as synonyms of 'cancellation'. They show, in fact, the same word usage in context and refer to ending a contract for the non-performance of contractual obligations. This is corroborated by the language of law in the UK. The Explanatory Notes to the Consumer Rights Act, 2015, for example, clearly states that “[contract] conditions, breach of which enables the consumer to choose either to treat the contract as terminated or to continue with the contract” (Explanatory Notes, 18); “. . . where a consumer cancels a contract (and is charged a so-called 'termination fee')” (*ibid.*, 71) and “Consumer may terminate contract if second failure.” (*ibid.*, 120).

4. Discussion

What emerged during the task performance, was the efforts made by the participants to formulate the search queries. In particular, they strove to grasp how each query needed formulation, and how each corpus was to be taught in order to find results. However, as soon as they understood what to search and how to write the search string correctly in each corpus, results were found easily and fast. It was the impression of the lecturer that more than depending on the participants' experience in (legal) translations, the ability to write the correct query syntax relied on their personal capability to understand and elaborate ICT commands. This does not mean that it was possible to translate legal words or expressions with no prior knowledge of the legal field, but that technological skills were very important in fulfilling the tasks proposed.

In light of the above, the attendants understood and appreciated how to search for terms in online legal corpora and increased both critical thinking and rationalization thanks to the joint use of different corpora (Giampieri, 2018b), and comparisons with multiple language and/or authoritative resources. This was underpinned by the final questionnaire, which showed a high level of satisfaction, comprehension, and commitment. Results from the questionnaire are discussed here.

As outlined above, at the end of the workshop the participants filled out a questionnaire. The questionnaire aimed at verifying the following factual, behavioral, and attitudinal information (Sanjun, 2016): (1) any previous knowledge of online corpora, (2) the linguistic tools used before the workshop, (3) the participants' level of satisfaction, and (4) their commitment to the new technological tools.

The first point to search was whether the participants had used and electronic translation tools before the workshop. Table 1 reports the findings.

Table 1
Electronic Translation Tools Used Before the Workshop

Electronic translation tools used so far	frequency
<i>Wordreference</i>	6 (2 lawyers)
<i>Google Translator</i>	6 (2 lawyers)
<i>Wikipedia</i>	5
<i>Online dictionaries (implemented by lexicographers)</i>	3 (2 lawyers)
<i>Bilingual paper dictionaries</i>	3
<i>Other tools:</i>	8
<i>Reverso</i>	2 (1 lawyer)
<i>Linguee</i>	2
<i>Iate</i>	1
<i>Eurlex</i>	1
<i>Proz</i>	1
<i>Google scholar</i>	1

Table 1 above highlights that most of the participants had used online tools which, if used uncritically, cannot be considered completely reliable (Genette, 2016). For example, *Wikipedia* is claimed to be a frequently consulted online tool whose linked resources, however, may not be trustworthy (Barnett, 2018). Other language tools, such as the online concordancers *Reverso* and *Linguee* are not implemented by lexicographers and may lead to inaccurate legal translations (Giampieri, 2016). In this regard, Genette (2016) suggests that only proficient users should consult online bilingual concordancers, as

they are able to eschew mistakes and question the translations proposed (*ibid.*, 82).

As far as *Wordreference* is concerned, for instance, it is claimed that it cannot always be considered reliable (Giampieri, 2016). The main reasons lie in the fact that it is not implemented by lexicographers, and it is not always grounded in linguistic research. The same can be said of *Google translator*. Amongst the other tools mentioned, some are not always reliable, such as *Eurlex*, *IATE*, *Reverso* and *Linguee*. *IATE* is *par excellence* the online dictionary of the EU institutions whereas *Eurlex* is the European database of EU law, with translations in all European languages. As can be easily guessed, these two online resources are grounded in EU translations, which, unfortunately, are not always consistent or trustworthy (Giampieri, 2016; *Studies on Translation and Multilingualism*, 2012; Wagner, 2010). This does not mean that we should simply disregard any potential usefulness of the world's most voluminous body of multilingual resources generated by professional translators who are selected on a very rigorous basis (see the work by Killman, 2017), but that mistranslations can occur due to the difficulties of harmonizing and adapting legal terms and concepts hallmarking different legal systems (Graziadei, 2015; Jacometti & Pozzo, 2018). In addition, this does not mean that translators should not consult multilingual platform such as *Eurlex*, or multilingual termbases (Melby, 2012) such as *IATE*, but that corpora should be considered as reliable supplements to other language resources (Frankenberg-Garcia, 2015). It is the opinion of the authors that online corpora are reliable language tools which can be used for legal translations, especially if used jointly (Giampieri, 2018b) and/or in conjunction with other language resources. What was most challenging to the participants was, perhaps, the writing of the search syntax itself.

Therefore, for the purpose of this trial lesson and for the reasons stated above, both *IATE* and *Eurlex* are not considered completely trustworthy, in particular if used without corpus consultation. The same applies to *Reverso* and *Linguee*, which are linguistic interfaces (or search engines), which sometimes draw on *Eurlex* translations. Hence, as can be inferred from Table 1 above, untrustworthy and/or non-lexicographical online materials top the list. In light of the above, it can be stated that, before the workshop, both professional translators and experienced lawyers could find the workshop topics beneficial, especially as far as technological tools for translations are concerned. This is corroborated by Table 2 here below.

The second concern of the questionnaire was to tap the participants' previous knowledge of corpora before the workshop; less than 50% of the participants knew and probably used *Google advanced search*, which, sometimes, can be used as a linguistic and translation tool (Ferraresi, 2009; Giampieri, 2018b).

No-one was acquainted with online legal corpora, instead. For this reason, all of the participants found the workshop useful. The reasons are mostly due to the fact that their knowledge and skills increased. Another aim of the questionnaire was to see if the participants would use online tools in future. It goes without saying that all of the participants declared their intent to use at least an online tool in their future translations. In particular, they indicated either the *BoLC* or the *Lextutor* corpora and the *BoLC* together. Also the need for further training came to the fore, which corroborates the findings of other researchers (cf., Gallego-Hernández, 2015). Finally, the questionnaire sought to find if the participants would share their new competences with their peers. 7 participants out of 8 were in favor of sharing the newly acquired competences with their peers. The only one reluctant stated that s/he works on his/her own. In light of the above, it is self-evident that not only was the workshop useful and fruitful, but it also highlighted the proneness to share the new skills.

5. Conclusion

This paper aimed at exploring whether a workshop on online monolingual legal corpora could equip translators and lawyers with technical skills and help them carry out legal translations more accurately. To this aim, a 3-hour workshop was organized and 8 participants (4 translators, 1 student in translation studies and 3 lawyers) attended the training. During the training session, they performed a few tasks on online corpora. The tasks brought to the fore a few important findings: (1) that dictionaries are not always reliable (cf., Andrades Moreno, 2013); (2) that learning how to formulate the queries in each corpus requires attention and precision; (3) that once it is understood how to write a search string, collocations and translation equivalents are relatively fast and easy to find; and (4) that both translators and lawyers need training in technological language tools. At the end of the workshop, in fact, the participants corroborated their need for further training in the field, mostly because they used to rely on untrustworthy online resources (see Table 1 above). Another important finding revolved around the fact that lawyers and translators helped each other in the performance of some tasks. Therefore, as highlighted by the literature, a desirable situation would be the one where lawyers translate and have their work edited by linguists or vice-versa. All in all, the participants found the workshop extremely useful and practical. As outlined above, their first efforts principally focused on a change of perspectives and on how to formulate the search query correctly in each corpus. After that, their increased knowledge was visible and applicable to the tasks which followed.

As for the limitations of the study, although it was only a trial lesson, it is nonetheless significant, as it represents a relevant contribution to both legal

translation research and education. This paper highlighted that technical competence can be a contributing factor in order to find acceptable translation candidates and deliver fine-grained legal translations. Therefore, online legal corpora training/coaching could be inserted into translation training curricula in order to help overcome the intricacies of the language of law, and provide users with the right tools to compensate for their shortcomings. Future research may encompass larger groups of the participants and longer training sessions, perhaps distributed over the long run, in order to assess performances and improvements. Due to the small sample size, generalizations cannot be drawn; however, this trial lesson could inform the design of larger scale studies on the topic.

Furthermore, the questionnaire results seem to rely heavily on the participants' perceptions. Nevertheless, some objective findings can be found. For example, the participants learned how to check frequencies in order to determine the best translation candidate(s) (cf., Frankenberg-Garcia, 2015) and understood how to look for collocations. They were also able to compare a variety of electronic language resources, such as dictionary entries and corpus findings. It goes without saying that it would only be possible to provide objective findings when the participants can use corpora satisfactorily. Nevertheless, their interest in using corpora in their future translations allows to speculate that they might find them beneficial. Furthermore, as anticipated above, another workshop with more participants could be organized in order to gather more data.

Another limitation of corpora is found in the corpora themselves. It is, in fact, argued that if a corpus is too small it may not be representative; i.e., it may not contain enough field-specific terms (cf., Melby, 2012). At the same time, if it is too large it may be distracting, or its suggestions may be in contrast with one another (*ibid.*); it is argued that legal corpora need not be large to be representative, given the fact that legal discourse is highly formulaic and repetitive (cf., Bhatia et al., 2004). On the other hand, if too large, users can always be taught how to “navigate” (Zanettin, 2001) through the data they deal with.

Other limitations lay in the duration of the workshop and in the heterogeneity of the participants. However, it is the opinion of the authors that 3 hours were enough to at least lay the foundations and help the participants approach a new term research method. Furthermore, as far as the heterogeneity of the group is concerned, the authors noticed that lawyers and translators helped each other while performing the tasks. Hence, heterogeneity should not be perceived as a weakness, but as a strength.

Finally, given the initial stage of the training, the lecturer did not feel the need to prompt the participants to also consider the differences between the

common law and the civil law systems, or any other differences in the law systems of English-speaking countries.

Notes:

1. http://ec.europa.eu/civiljustice/comp_crime_victim/comp_crime_victim_ger_en.htm
2. See also https://www.supremecourt.tas.gov.au/publications/speeches/estcour_j/pleading_tips_and_tricks

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